

GOVERNING NET ZERO MISSIONS

Innovation, Alignment, and Mobilisation Insights from Bristol and Fellow Cities

JOEL TERWILLIGER | NET ZERO FUTURES BRIEF SERIES NO.4 OF 5

RESEARCH FOCUS AND POLICY CONTEXT

'Mission cities' show considerable innovation in governance approaches: portfolios of climate interventions, 'radical collaboration' across sectors, and learning-led acceleration toward net zero. Bristol pursued this approach across two support networks—the EU NetZeroCities (NZC) and the Innovate UK Net Zero Living (NZL) platforms—navigating a complex policy landscape with an identified £7.8 billion investment need. Drawing on 16 stakeholder views across Bristol's public, knowledge and advisory, and VCSE sectors—with comparative insights from fellow Mission cities and NZL places—this brief examines how mission governance is actually experienced. Its central finding: mission delivery depends not primarily on new tools but on the sustained, chronically under-resourced 'people work' of cross-sector alignment. Without structural support, compliance-level governance becomes the default, leaving the innovation needed for genuine net zero transformation incomplete or stalled.

KEY FINDINGS

Behind every tool are 'anchor people' trying to make it work—each carrying distinct perspectives, from institutional mandates and investor criteria to resident needs. Cities navigate austerity and risk aversion; knowledge and advisory actors prioritise bankability criteria that marginalise hyper-local solutions; and civil society advocates for trust-based interventions structurally resistant to rapid scaling. Mission-readiness—the challenge of innovating city capabilities, including translating different institutional languages, to govern missions—stems from cities' own journeys, not top-down missions: of the 31 Mission Label cities with published plans, 28 had a climate action journey of nine or more years before joining. Bristol's enabling ecosystem—a neutral broker network, embedded research/advocacy, thriving VCSE sector, core funding—took decades to build and cannot be shortcut. The journey from co-produced community priorities to investment-ready plans is where mission governance can stall—and where the gap between equitable partnership in principle and power relations in practice signals lengthier conversations are needed.

KEY MESSAGES FOR POLICY AND PRACTICE

- **A UK statutory local authority climate duty—or national equivalent—with dedicated resourcing is needed to ensure local mission delivery.** Without it, cities either absorb the cost of governance innovation, default to compliance-level governance, or deliver partial, uneven processes based on existing resources that all risk derailing the net zero agenda. The fragmented, short-term, and competitive funding landscape remains a primary barrier to local delivery.
- **Actors speak fundamentally different languages—and translation is the missing infrastructure.** Understanding where logics align or diverge, and what it takes to bridge them is often where mission governance succeeds or fails — and that understanding must be built deliberately through mutual learning mechanisms that acknowledge and manage cross-sector friction, not assumed.
- **Map enabling conditions and identify systemic gaps.** Prioritise where new investments in intermediation and shared infrastructure are most needed — including designing regional finance innovations with explicit conditionality on community benefit and just transition outcomes.
- **Build cross-programme collaboration into funding architecture—and sustain what's been built.** The institutional knowledge and networks programmes like NetZeroCities and Net Zero Living generated took years to build — sustaining, updating, and translating those outputs is essential to avoid cities duplicating learning and relearning costly lessons about what works when funding ends.

BRISTOL'S INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM AND MULTI-LEVEL POLICY CONTEXT

The NZF study took a triple helix approach to examining net zero mission governance—gathering views from three stakeholder clusters directly involved in delivering or supporting the Bristol NZIC Lab (NetZeroCities, 2023): Bristol City Council working with their regional counterpart, the West of England Combined Authority (WECA) (public sector); consultancies, think tanks, and finance specialists, including NZC experts and Innovate UK NZL partners (knowledge and advisory); and community anchor organisations (CAOs), social enterprises, and just transition advocates (VCSE sector). This approach focused on the institutional

logics—governance, financial/technical, and community/legitimacy respectively—of each cluster because understanding the lived experiences of actors and how these logics interact and diverge is essential for identifying what mission governance requires in practice. Knowledge and advisory partners in particular brought comparative insights from working with multiple NZC Mission cities and NZL places across the UK, some active in both support ecosystems—making the analysis comparative as well as case-based. **Figure 1** maps the four innovation domains across which these three clusters were active.

Figure 1. The Bristol Innovation Ecosystem: Innovation Types & Activities. Own Illustration.

Bristol's innovation activities are situated within a multi-level policy context (key UK elements mapped in **Figure 2**). At the EU level, the NZC Pilot Cities Programme (PCP) (NetZeroCities, no date) provided mission templates, consortium technical assistance, and peer learning networks for the Bristol Lab. In the UK context, the Innovate UK NZL programme funded the Mission Net Zero demonstrator (BCC, 2023), which alongside NZL partners provided its own peer learning via the FutureReady community of practice (Liminal, 2023) and delivered a blueprint for key net zero governance processes. These two support ecosystems overlapped—sharing the Bristol Lab as an experimental hub for workstreams—but remained distinct in their funding, accountability, and technical assistance structures.

At the national level, the 2021 net zero strategy (BEIS, 2021) and 2023 review (Skidmore, 2023) were followed by several key developments. These included local area and regional energy planning and industrial plans associated with the UK Clean Energy Superpower Mission (DESNZ, 2025a), the formation of the National Wealth Fund (IfG, 2025), and the UK Net Zero Public Participation Strategy (DESNZ, 2025b). At the regional level, Bristol coordinates with WECA and stakeholders on climate action and investment planning activities. These include co-developing the regional Green Growth West Fund and Bristol Mission Net Zero project activities, namely: 1) co-developing a Regional Investment Plan; 2) exploring community-led approaches to developing

Figure 2. Bristol's Multi-Level Climate Policy Context. Own Illustration.

neighbourhood level project pipelines via a Community Climate Investment Plan (CCIP) mechanism; and, 3) finding alignment points between regional, city, and community plans to inform identifying priorities to develop/incorporate into “investible buckets” or portfolio pipelines. At the local level, Bristol's One City approach and CCC provided the strategic framework within which all four projects operated.

As Bristol's own CCC policy assessment notes (BCC, 2025a, pp. 18–19), there is 'not a nested approach in the UK where national policy informs a coherent programme of linked national, regional, and local action'—making the dual EU/UK mission support that much more significant, and its absence that much more consequential for less well-connected cities.

The Growing ‘Mission-Readiness’ Narrative: Public Sector Innovation Can ‘Save The World’

This multi-level policy architecture must be understood in the context of a growing narrative in climate governance around ‘mission-readiness’ (European Commission, 2024, pp. 19, 21): the multistakeholder journey whereby cities develop the enabling conditions — city networks, strategic planning, GHG inventories, research and innovation projects, climate mainstreaming, stakeholder engagement, partnerships, and monitoring systems — that allow them to play a facilitating role in driving large-scale net zero transformation. The key EU Mission for 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities (EU Cities Mission) assumption is that supporting structures and processes of public sector innovation at all levels can build capacity to implement net zero transformations — in effect, that public sector innovation can ‘save the world’ (Terwilliger and Christie, 2025).

However, there are recognised gaps in cities' skills, capabilities, and resources in areas such as participation, monitoring systems, and climate finance (Innovate UK and GFI, 2022, p. 7; European Commission, 2024, p. 18) that the NZC platform was designed to address. The NZF study's analysis of 31 Mission Label awardee cities (Figure 3) puts this assumption in sharp relief: of the first two cohorts of awardees, 28 of 31 had been engaged in a climate action journey for nine years or more before joining the Mission, with 10 active in the climate space for two decades or more. Mission-readiness, in other words, is not something a top-down Mission produces — it is something cities bring to it, built over years of foundational activity. Cities are also incentivised by funders to produce highly ambitious plans that outpace their operational realities, both in terms of 2030 targets (Eckersley et al., 2025) and city-to-regional collaborative governance (Vanhuysse, Piseddu and Jokiahho, 2023). This is the context in which the Bristol enabling ecosystem findings that follow must be read.

Figure 3. Building Mission-Readiness: Foundational Climate Action Journeys of 31 Mission Label Cities

The Bristol Net Zero Investment Co-Innovation Lab

Bristol's work across UK and EU support ecosystems was organised through four overlapping funded projects that ran through the Bristol Lab (outlined in Table 1). Each brought distinct funding, partners, and accountability

requirements—but shared delivery infrastructure, key personnel, and interconnected outputs. Understanding how these projects related to each other is important context for the cross-sector findings that follow.

Table 1

The Bristol Net Zero Investment Co-Innovation Lab: Key Funded Projects and Milestones

Project	Key Milestones	Funder
Community Climate Action (CCA) Project <i>Oct 2020 – Jul 2025</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cohort 1: 6 CCAPs launched (Jun 2022) – Cohort 2: 5 CCAPs launched (Apr 2024) – Cohort 3: 6 CCAPs launched (Jun 2025) – CCA Model + insights published (Nov 2025) 	National Lottery Climate Action Fund (UK)
EU Mission for 100 Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities <i>Apr 2022 – May 2025</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – CCC submitted to European Commission (Sep 2024) – CCC awarded Mission Label (May 2025) 	Horizon Europe
Net Zero Investment Co-Innovation Lab <i>Jun 2023 – May 2025</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Bristol City Leap case study (Sep 2024) – Green Growth West Fund initiated/approved by WECA (Sep 2024) – NZC City Expert Support contract (Oct 2024–Apr 2025) – Bristol Community and Nature Action Initiative (BCAI) launch (Mar/May 2025) 	Horizon Europe
Mission Net Zero Demonstrator Project <i>Apr 2024 – Nov 2025</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Annual gathering presentation and reflection (Nov 2024) – Community energy workshop series for 12 local VCSEs (Jan–Jun 2025) – Just Transition in Action Model published (Jun 2025) 	Innovate UK (Net Zero Living Programme)

The four projects that ran through the Bristol Lab were not sequential—they overlapped significantly across a five-year period and developed shared outputs that built on each other. The Community Climate Action (CCA) Project (BCNP, no date) provided the community engagement infrastructure and the 17 Community Climate Action Plans (CCAPs) described in **Brief 3**—and the Community Leadership Panel (BCNP and Praxis, 2024) it co-developed became a governance mechanism used across the other projects. The EU Cities Mission work produced the One City CCC (EC, 2025), Bristol's primary city-level procedural governance tool (PGT) framing the overarching strategic and investment planning aspirations that were further articulated, co-developed, and tested with project partners and stakeholders.

The NZC PCP project—Bristol NZIC Lab—was the financial innovation hub: it developed the Green Growth West Fund (via Bristol & Bath Regional Capital into a £100m WECA impact fund) (BBRC and Amber Infrastructure Group, 2024), explored the Carbon Multiplier Fund concept, launched the Bristol Climate Action Investment (BCAI) citizen crowdfunding mechanism (BCC, 2025b), and

engaged NZC City Expert Support (NetZeroCities, 2024). The Mission Net Zero demonstrator added the Net Zero Neighbourhood (NZN) Model (3Ci, 2023) as a fourth mechanism—a place-based regeneration approach to scaling housing retrofits developed through 3Ci and partners—and explored with three CCA organisations.

The overlapping structure of these projects—distinct in funding and accountability but shared in delivery (as **Table 1** illustrates)—meant that the governance challenge of the Bristol Lab was not simply about running four projects in parallel. It was about maintaining coherence across different funders' requirements, different theories of change, and different stakeholder expectations, while the underlying work of building trust, developing shared frameworks, and aligning community and institutional priorities was being done simultaneously. The 16 stakeholder interviews that underpin this brief traced that lived experience across all four projects and both support ecosystems—revealing the people work required for aligning and progressing the Bristol ecosystem.

CROSS-SECTOR THEMES, INSIGHTS, AND IMPLICATIONS

The 16 stakeholder interviews conducted across the three Bristol delivery and design actor clusters reveal not just different approaches to net zero, but genuinely different institutional logics—each with its own framing of the problem, metrics for success,

and set of constraints. **Tables 2–4** below present condensed findings from each sector, drawing on thematic analysis of interview data and triangulation with documents, observations, and digital media.

Public Sector Perspectives: Between Institutional Inertia and Governance Innovation

Table 2

Public Sector Perspectives

Theme	Core Insight	Implication
Feet in Two Worlds	Local authorities (LAs) operate between 'business as usual' institutional constraints and emerging innovation-led governance practices	<i>Change is incremental, emerging at the margins rather than through systemic transformation</i>
Building an Internal Mandate	Developing internal buy-in and a shared theory of change is a gradual, relational process within and beyond the city	<i>Internal alignment is foundational to scaling outward and coordinating across stakeholders</i>
Council–CAO Partnership Model	A hybrid 'top-down meets bottom-up' model is emerging through brokerage between city and community actors	<i>Traditional top-down governance is insufficient; new intermediary-led and hybrid approaches are needed</i>
Mediating Engagement Tensions	Engagement processes must balance competing demands between strategic objectives and community priorities	<i>The city plays a critical role managing trade-offs between inclusivity, legitimacy, and delivery</i>
Aligning Across Scales	Integrated portfolios are new and complex, requiring 'a lengthy conversation' balancing multi-level priorities	<i>Efforts to align across scales are shaped by investment logics, creating trade-offs between delivery and equitable outcomes</i>

Public sector actors describe governance innovation as a relational project as much as an institutional one. Building the internal mandate for net zero—across departments, political cycles, and officer cultures—requires sustained investment in relationship-building, translation, and coalition formation. This 'internal alignment' work is frequently underestimated in resources and time required yet is foundational to effective external partnership and coordination. Hybrid governance models—where Transition Teams, Community Leadership Panels, and CAO partnerships create new forms of co-governance—are promising but fragile and dependent on individual champions. The NZC-inspired Transition Team structure (Wainwright et al., 2022) and its UK Local Climate

Commission counterpart (PCAN, 2024) both are designed to play a multi-sector coordination role in governance but have no decision-making power over cities. Equally, cities have no authority to compel organisations across the city to engage and resource (beyond their own organisations) key collaborative climate action governance activities, such as project development, shared monitoring systems, or co-investment in shared priorities. New PGTs (e.g., the CCC, CCIP) designed to link regional, city, and community scales of climate action and investment planning are innovative but introduce complexity and tensions around public and private value, requiring a lengthier conversation with communities and stakeholders.

Knowledge and Advisory Sector: Finance as the Defining Challenge

The knowledge and advisory sector frames the net zero transition primarily as a finance mobilisation challenge. The scale of the challenge they are responding to is significant: as Brief 2 documents, the EU Cities Mission Capital Hub estimates €310 billion is needed for the 100 Mission cities to reach net zero by 2030, with 90% expected from private

capital—a gap so large that it shapes which co-benefits and interventions are prioritised. A key financial innovation vehicle proposed to bridge the public-private divide is the 'Portfolio Approach.' Financial experts recognise that private investments historically cherry-pick lucrative assets (e.g., solar PV) while leaving low- or negative-return social infrastructure (e.g., active travel infrastructure, residential retrofits) to the public sector. The portfolio model intentionally bundles both. While this lowers returns, portfolios in theory remain attractive to private investors to co-invest with cities. Synthesised themes are given in [Table 3](#).

Table 3
Knowledge and Advisory Sector Perspectives

Theme	Core Insight	Implication
The 'Horribly Large' Finance Gap	Financial innovation (FI) reframes the climate challenge as a problem of structuring & mobilising investment at scale	<i>The transition is framed as a public finance gap problem that financial innovation models can solve</i>
Governing Blended Portfolios	FI models introduce tensions in how public and private interests—risk, return, and public value—are negotiated	<i>Delivering FIs depends on reconciling tensions between financial returns and non-return-generating projects</i>
Making the Case: Co-Benefits and Bankability	Co-benefits are used to improve the socioeconomic case for climate action and attract investment	<i>Value remains contested and unevenly applied, limiting consistent integration of social outcomes, with 'cherry-picking' risks remaining</i>
Building the Pipeline	Project pipelines are geared toward institutional investors and scaled propositions, with marginal citizen inclusion	<i>Priorities are decided through an 'investable' lens, with smaller-scale and just transition considerations at the margins</i>
Bankability Mismatches	Mismatches arise between 'bankable' criteria and local project realities; LAs may not be best placed to develop portfolios	<i>What counts as value is contested; criteria mismatches and local delivery gaps are systemic challenges</i>
Embedding Social Value & Hope	Social outcomes are often incorporated indirectly or instrumentally—conductive to improved business cases—within FI models	<i>Social value creation remains secondary rather than structurally embedded in investment logic</i>
Limits to Scaling	Scaling FI models is limited by systemic factors & requires higher-level policy signals	<i>Misaligned policy ambitions and signals ultimately constrain FI scalability</i>

By aggregating these into a single, scaled investment vehicle such as the Green Growth West Fund, the overall return can be slightly diluted, but the risk is redistributed, allowing private capital to inadvertently cross-subsidise public sector obligations alongside public oversight of criteria. However, translating community desires into these high-finance portfolios is fraught with difficulty. Fund managers explicitly noted that while pooling community-scale projects is desirable, the ‘politics involved and the energy to get things off the

ground can be quite difficult,’ rendering them fundamentally un-bankable without immense pre-development work and risk-absorption by the municipality. Ultimately, experts concluded that social value outcomes and co-benefits must be ‘baked in’ to the governance of financial innovation models—and that policy ambitions at Mission level must be matched by clear investment signals from sovereign and public-oriented institutions such as the National Wealth Fund and European Investment Bank.

VCSE Sector: Community Infrastructure as the Foundation of Legitimacy

VCSE sector actors offer a fundamentally different perspective on net zero mission governance. Rather than framing the transition as a finance problem, they frame it as a legitimacy problem: without genuine community ownership, without trusted relationships between cities and residents, and without governance structures that give marginalised communities real agency, net zero transitions will be imposed rather than co-created—and will fail to deliver the just transition

that both social equity and long-term political sustainability require. Community anchor organisations (CAOs) played a critical bridging role in this context. With capacity building support through projects like CCA, they can leverage their trust with residents, understand the language and logic of local government, and translate between community priorities and institutional processes to co-produce solutions that are fit for purpose. Key VCSE stakeholder themes are outlined in [Table 4](#).

Table 4
Voluntary, Community, and Social Enterprise Sector Perspectives

Theme	Core Insight	Implication
Strategic Role of CAOs	CAOs act as trusted intermediaries translating climate agendas into locally meaningful action and building a 'social mandate'	<i>Community infrastructure is essential for grounding climate action in legitimacy and lived experience</i>
Community-Led Climate Planning	Co-production redistributes and amplifies local voice and agency but requires significant time, trust, and capacity	<i>Inclusive engagement can reshape decision-making, but authenticity is resource-intensive</i>
Rebalancing Urban Governance	CAOs build broader coalitions by linking existing local actions with climate and social impacts; place-based knowledge and lived experience are under-valued in governance	<i>CAO expertise is critical to build legitimacy, local support, and context-sensitive solutions informed by diverse community insights</i>
CAO–Council Partnership	New collaboration depends on mutual learning between LAs and CAOs to jointly address barriers	<i>New partnership models bridge fundamentally different logics: technical net zero vs. just transition, social</i>
One City Challenges	Fragmented systems, finance gaps, and unclear roles create a gap between strategy and delivery	<i>System-level coordination and resource challenges constrain implementation</i>
Just Transition in Action	Efforts emerging to embed equity through co-benefits and inclusive planning frameworks	<i>A more meaningful operationalisation of just transition principles has potential but remains conceptual</i>
Limits of the CAO–Council Model	Scaling is constrained by capacity, funding precarity, role ambiguity, and mission misalignments	<i>While hybrid models improve delivery prospects, structural constraints limit scalability; working in isolation risks 'social backlash'</i>

CAOs' legitimacy as trusted intermediaries is their most valuable and most fragile asset; it is built over years and can be eroded rapidly by tokenistic engagement or unfulfilled commitments. Even CAO-council partnerships with dedicated resource face structural constraints around scaling, replication, and accountability that cannot be resolved at the project level alone. In the Bristol

context this manifested at the mission level, where CAOs must carefully consider their core (often social) missions and avoid mission drift and city and VCSE sector missions don't always perfectly align. When considering the prospect of scaling in Bristol or replicating elsewhere, organisational capacity, 'episodic' or precarious funding, and role ambiguity are key barriers.

NAVIGATING THE 'PEOPLE WORK' OF THE TRANSITION: COMPETING LOGICS IN CLIMATE MOBILISATION

The economic scale of urban climate action creates a structural problem for local government. Fulfilling the UK's carbon targets necessitates sustained, massive private investment supported by credible long-term policy signals and state-backed risk-sharing mechanisms. Recognising the inability of the public purse to shoulder this burden, initiatives like the National Wealth Fund and the UK Net Zero Public Participation Strategy aim to crowd-in private capital while attempting to secure democratic consent. However, the reality of local government finance is defined by a decade of austerity, severely depleting the capacities and capabilities necessary to structure complex financial deals or manage multifaceted public-private partnerships.

These pressures produce three distinct but interacting institutional logics that must be actively reconciled. Public authorities are constrained by

fiscal austerity, risk aversion, and rigid legislative compliance frameworks, forcing them to prioritise scalable, revenue-generating projects to satisfy fiduciary duties and optimise public spend. Knowledge and advisory actors advocate for large-scale financial innovations with "bankability" criteria that frequently marginalise bespoke, hyper-local solutions due to high transaction costs. Meanwhile, civil society actors advocate for trust-based, highly tailored interventions that address local inequalities but are structurally resistant to rapid scaling. **Figure 4** synthesises the cross-sectoral themes from the previous section and key normative questions facing each sector—and makes explicit what is often hidden in governance narratives: that alignment across these systems is not a technical exercise but an ongoing, contested process requiring significant relational 'people work' over the long term.

Figure 4. The 'People Work' of the Transition: Reconciling Governance, Financial, and Social Innovation Approaches. Own Illustration.

Resolving these tensions is not straightforward—specifically, the aggregation of diverse projects into blended-finance portfolios is complex and assumes a reversal of commonplace cherry-picking behaviour in favour of pioneering experimental, large-scale cross-sectoral models that distribute risks and rewards. Proponents of these models seek to crowd-in the 90% private investment through aggregating Mission city projects in a particular country, or pooling similar projects across Mission cities in a regional area, but currently these are untried and untested models. While experts argue the resources are out there but need to be aligned and organised, the specifics of where the 90% will come from remains an open question. The NZF study identified the cultivation of ‘productive margins’ where cross-sectoral compromises can be negotiated (covered in Brief 5) as a promising area for building on the knowledge and momentum gained across Mission support ecosystems.

This ‘people work’ includes building trust between actors with fundamentally different languages, priorities, and accountability structures; negotiating

trade-offs explicitly rather than displacing them; translating between community knowledge and institutional processes; and developing shared visions of what a just transition should actually entail in Bristol's specific context and beyond. These processes are essential for bridging competing logics—but they are often hidden, under-recognised, and under-resourced in relation to dominant, top-down approaches to net zero. This has direct implications for how ‘success’ in mission governance is measured. If monitoring systems track only carbon reductions, investment mobilised, or technology deployed, the ‘people work’ that makes these outcomes possible—and sustainable—remains invisible and unvalued. Building it into governance design from the outset, and explicitly resourcing it, is a crucial foundation. Without concerted efforts to reconcile these disparate logics and confront assumptions, the ambitious targets set by local governments will remain unfunded, undeliverable, and at risk of being derailed by social and political backlash.

WHAT MADE IT POSSIBLE: SUCCESS FACTORS AND THE JOURNEY TO AN ENABLING ECOSYSTEM

The NZF study's empirical work revealed that Bristol's progress in mission governance was not simply a product of the support structures on offer—it depended on a set of pre-existing and deliberately cultivated enabling conditions that took years to build. Understanding these conditions matters not only for appreciating what Bristol achieved, but for being honest about what other places would need to invest in before they could expect similar outcomes.

Key enabling factors identified by interviewees included: the Bristol Climate & Nature Partnership's (BCNP) role as a neutral, non-issue-specific broker and convening space—distinct from both the council and any single project, and therefore able to hold relationships across sectors over time; dedicated advocacy and research capacity embedded in organisations like the Centre for Sustainable Energy, providing the technical depth and sustained engagement with policy that city officers alone cannot sustain; a thriving VCSE sector already active in the climate space, with trusted relationships between community organisations and the council built over years of collaboration; and core funding over successive periods that allowed internal and external buy-in, climate and energy focused staff, and institutional capacity to be built up incrementally.

Collaboration between the council and CAOs also required early investment in defining shared ways of working and roles—agreed and written down at the start of the CCA project—grounded in shared values: mutual respect, honesty, transparency, and

a commitment to learning together. From Bristol's perspective, their primary role was as project manager and broker: ‘enabling, unlocking, unblocking, and finding the right people,’ helping CAOs navigate the silos and structures of a large local authority. From the VCSE perspective, CAOs functioned as trusted messengers building a durable social mandate—while the council provided access to resources, data, and expertise that CAOs could not access alone. Together with the BCNP's neutral broker role facilitating cross-sector connections, these were the enabling infrastructure without which the tools and frameworks described in Brief 3 could not function. As one officer stated: ‘you could run a project without it, but it enables a project in a way that's very hard to replicate through a more transactional arrangement.’

Several mechanisms and framings propelled the partnership. The Community Leadership Panel—combining Governance and Social innovation, Participatory and Integrative REPAIR dimensions—was the mechanism through which community insights formally shaped wider strategic policy and decision-making. A capacity-building programme mentored diverse ‘non-climate-specialist’ CAOs, embedding the Learning and Social innovation necessary for sustained engagement. The Memorandum of Understanding between Bristol City Council and BCNP committed Bristol to being an enabler rather than a barrier across all departments—a structural mechanism to embed working in partnership beyond individual projects.

A further mechanism directly connects to the Net Zero Neighbourhood (NZN) model discussed in **Brief 3**: the 'climate by stealth' approach—engaging communities initially via energy, nature, food, health, and social isolation rather than leading with climate—mirrors what one NZN designer described as a 'Trojan horse regeneration programme in which you do retrofit.' Both framings reflect the same political and behavioural logic: co-benefits must be the primary narrative, with net zero as the means rather than the message. The fact that this approach emerged independently in both the community-led CCA project and the financially-driven NZN model is a significant finding—suggesting it is not merely a community engagement preference but a structural requirement of any mission governance approach that aims to build genuine public consent.

A related and frank finding at the intersection of social and financial innovation concerns the gap between community engagement work and investment-readiness. Knowledge and advisory partners working on the Mission Net Zero project were candid that bridging CCAPs to Community Climate Investment Plans (CCIPs) is where things get most difficult: community organisations are 'very comfortable in the community climate action plan space—working out what people want, advocating for local residents.' But 'the jump to the investment bit, and the ownership of actions' is where progress stalls. Specialist skills—investment structuring, procurement, risk planning—are not typically located within community organisations, and building that capacity was described as potentially a ten-year journey.

The corollary is not that community organisations are inadequate partners for investment planning, but that mission governance must be designed with that gap explicitly in mind: providing dedicated, embedded project development support; resourcing the brokerage between community ambition and financial structuring; and expecting the journey from CCAP to CCIP to take multiple funding cycles rather than a single project period.

The central implication for other places is clear but often underestimated: these enabling conditions are replicable, but they cannot be copied overnight. As one interviewee put it, 'the reason Bristol's doing all this stuff is that a series of decisions have been made over 20–30 years to do that'—a sustainability team of eight to ten officers, strong relationships, and a VCSE sector already active in the climate space long before the mission programmes arrived. Bristol's own experience within the CCA project is instructive: Cohort 1 organisations had a very different and harder journey than Cohorts 2 and 3, who could build on the infrastructure, processes, and learning already established. Even within a single city, the capacity-building journey is iterative and cumulative. Other cities cannot simply 'flip a switch' and arrive at Bristol's enabling ecosystem. Foundational activities—building neutral convening spaces, growing a climate-capable VCSE sector, sustaining advocacy and research functions, progressively embedding climate into institutional culture—must be invested in over time. The journey cannot be skipped; the Bristol case offers an in-depth example of what that journey looks like and what it requires.

What's Next in the Series

This is **Brief 4** of the NZF Series, summarising the doctoral thesis of Joel Terwilliger: **Towards More Participatory Net Zero Futures (2022-2026)**, supervised by Ian Christie, Stelvia Matos, and Subhes Bhattacharyya. The series covers: (**Brief 1**) Contemporary Urban Governance Innovation Design: Principles, Tools, and an Innovation Typology; (**Brief 2**) Valuing What Matters in Urban Climate Governance: Co-Benefits Gaps and Functions in Making the Case for Action; (**Brief 3**) Governing a Just Net Zero Transition: The Bristol Toolkit and City and Community Visions for Change; (**Brief 4**) **Governing Net Zero Missions: Innovation, Alignment, and Mobilisation Insights from Bristol and Fellow Cities**; and (**Brief 5**) Missions, Myths, and Contemporary Procedural Governance Tools: Reflections and a Proposed Research Agenda.

KEY INSIGHTS & POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

For National Policymakers

- Establish a statutory local authority climate duty with resources to match. Without it, cities either absorb the cost of governance innovation, default to the compliance-level, or deliver partial, uneven processes based on existing resources that all risk derailing the net zero agenda. The fragmented, short-term, and competitive funding landscape remains a primary barrier to local delivery.
- Design regional finance innovations with explicit conditionality on community benefit and just transition outcomes — not only carbon and finance targets. Making the link between investment decisions and community priorities more practical is an urgent next step (see UK Co-Benefits Atlas, Phillips et al., 2025).
- Institutionalise cross-ecosystem peer learning beyond individual programme cycles. Mission governance knowledge generated through NZC and NZL lives in project outputs and practitioner networks that dissolve after grant periods — this infrastructure needs sustaining beyond time-limited funding.
- Invest in the pre-conditions for radical collaboration. The 'people work' of building trust across sectors is the mechanism through which governance, financial, and social innovation logics are brought into productive alignment — and mission platforms should assess whether cities have the foundational enabling conditions in place before assuming new tools or frameworks will be sufficient.

For Mission-Minded Cities and Practitioners

- Identify and empower 'anchor people' to champion climate action and treat net zero mandate-building as a multi-year governance investment — making it visible in theories of change, budget lines, and performance management frameworks from the start of mission-oriented initiatives.
- Map existing enabling conditions and identify systemic gaps across governance, financial, social, and learning innovation domains — prioritising where these are weakly connected and where new investments in alignment, intermediation, or shared infrastructure are most needed.
- Establish mutual learning mechanisms between existing and prospective organisational stakeholders to acknowledge and manage cross-sector friction — building the shared understanding of challenges, constraints, and productive margins within which collaborative solutions can develop.

For Funders and Finance Actors

- Fund the enabling ecosystem, not just the outputs it produces. Neutral broker organisations, embedded research and advocacy functions, and the sustained cross-sector relationships that make mission governance work are chronically underfunded relative to the strategies and investment plans they enable — and should be treated as core infrastructure costs, not overheads.
- Build incentives for cross-programme collaboration into funding architecture. Mission cities navigating multiple overlapping support ecosystems — NZC, NZL, C40, regional programmes — need funders to require alignment between programmes, build interoperability into grant conditions, and assess whether new tools are genuinely adding value or reproducing fragmentation under a different name.
- Take a programme rather than project view of mission momentum. The enabling conditions that mission delivery depends on — trust, capacity, shared theory of change — took years to develop and can be rapidly eroded by funding gaps or programme transitions. Build in explicit transition planning to protect ecosystem gains when individual project funding ends.

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